

ANALYSIS OF SHEAR DEFORMATION AND STRENGTH AT FIBER CROSSING PART IN TEXTILE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Woven, knitted and braided fabric, in spite of differences on fabrication process and mechanical behavior, are fabricated by intertwining the fiber bundle and the whole structure consists of repeat of crossing fiber bundles. Clearly the deformation and fracture behavior at fiber crossing part control the mechanical behavior of textile composite, so that it is important to understand the behavior at fiber crossing part quantitatively. In this study, for the purpose of investigating the behavior at fiber crossing part in textile composites, the evaluation method of the interface between fiber bundles was examined by numerical approaches. The effects of fiber undulation and modulus of interface between fiber bundles on shear deformation and strength at fiber crossing part was examined. Finally, a new attempt was performed that the strength of interface was calculated by combining the numerical and experimental approach.

KEYWORDS: textile composite, fiber crossing part, finite element method, interface property, crimp ratio, fiber bundle pull-out test

INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, advanced composite structures have been fabricated from tape prepregs which were systematically stacked to form a laminate. Two limitations of laminated composites provide much of the drive for the interest in "textile composite". First, the laying up of prepreg has been difficult to automate and it still an expensive and time consuming task. Second, the strength of some laminated structures is dominated by a relatively weak resistance to transverse shear, which is governed primarily by the matrix. Various forms of textile composites, which are reinforced with woven, knitted and braided fabric preform, have been considered through much of the modern composite history. It is believed that a properly designed textile composite would be relatively easy to automate and have a greater transverse strength than a laminated composite.

Woven, knitted and braided fabric, in spite of differences on fabrication process and mechanical behavior, are fabricated by intertwining the fiber bundle and the whole structure consists of repeat of crossing fiber bundles. Therefore, the fiber crossing is an invariable structure in textile composites. Because of the fiber crossing in textile composites, the undulation (crimp) of fiber bundles is generated and the particular transmission mechanism of force between fiber bundles is produced. The stress applied to one fiber bundle is transmitted

to another fiber bundle at the fiber crossing part. The deformation and fracture behavior at fiber crossing part control the mechanical behavior of textile composites, so that it is important to understand the behavior at fiber crossing part quantitatively. However, the architecture of a textile fabric in textile composite is complex and, therefore, the parameters controlling the behavior at fiber crossing part become numerous. Moreover, the behavior at fiber crossing part is dependent on the properties of interface between fiber and matrix.

Hamada et al have proposed a evaluation method of the interface between fiber bundles in woven fabric composite experimentally [1]. In the special experimental method, the shear strength of interface between warp fiber strand and weft fiber strand in a plain woven fabric with different concentration of silane coupling agents was obtained.

In this study, for the purpose of investigating the deformation and fracture behavior at fiber crossing part in textile composites, the evaluation method of the interface between fiber bundles was examined by numerical approaches. Firstly, the concept of modeling and numerical analysis model for textile composite is proposed. Second, the evaluation method proposed by Hamada et al. [1] was introduced as a background. The numerical analysis model was applied to the evaluation method. In this paper, the effects of fiber undulation and modulus of interface between fiber bundles on shear deformation and strength at fiber crossing part was examined. Finally, a new attempt was performed that the strength of interface was calculated by combining the numerical and experimental approach.

MODELING FOR TEXTILE COMPOSITES

In the case of textile composites, fiber orientation angle, crimp, continuity of fiber and stress transmission system between fibers greatly affect the mechanical behavior. So, the analytical model has to represent the weaving structure faithfully. Moreover, various range of fractures from microscopic fracture to macroscopic fracture in the composite have to be considered. It might be difficult to represent all ranges of fracture in a single model. In conformity with the concept, we have established an unified method from micro model to macro model [2-4]. Figure 1 shows the five modeling steps for simulating the mechanical behaviors of the braided composite precisely. Basically, results obtained from micro models are used in the analyses of macro models. According to this system, macroscopic analysis can be performed considering microscopic phenomena. Hereafter, specific characteristics of each model are described.

"Fiber bundle model" represents the fiber bundle impregnated with resin. This model does not consider the undulation of fiber bundle, although micro fracture in the fiber bundle can be considered by using the model. This model might consider micro phenomena such as the effects of surface treatment, filament diameter and number of filaments.

Fig.1 Five modeling steps for simulating mechanical behaviors of braided composites.

"Cross part model" represents the cross part between fiber bundles to consider the effects of the contact between undulated fiber bundles and interface between fiber and matrix. This model might consider the cross sectional shape of fiber bundle, weaving structure and interfacial properties at the cross part between fiber bundles.

"Weaving structural model" represents the weaving structure to consider its effect on the mechanical behavior of braided composites. The braided composites are recognized as an aggregation of the resin impregnated fiber bundle and resin region. The weaving structure of the braided composites is expressed as connections to beam elements. Resin existing between crossing fiber bundles is set by using beam element because of considering transmission of force at crossing point between the fiber bundles and the material constants of

the resin element will be obtained by analysis of "Cross part model". The resin elements are also set up in both surfaces of textile composite since the resin exists at surface of the textile composite except for between crossing fiber bundles.

"Basic structural model" represents the basic braided composite such as flat or tubular braided composite. The mechanical behavior of the basic braided composites can be predicted by using the numerical results of the weaving structural models as material constants and failure criteria. Finally "Structural model" represents the whole structure of braided composite. Numerical results of the weaving structural models or basic structural model, can be used as material constants of each element in the structural model. This analytical method can be applied to predict the various mechanical properties of braided composite, by selecting and combining these models according to the analytical objects.

BACKGROUND - FIBER BUNDLE PULL-OUT TEST -

Hamada et al have proposed a new evaluation method of the interface between fiber bundles in textile composites, called "Fiber bundle pull-out test" [1]. Through the fiber bundle pull-out test, the shear strength at fiber crossing part in textile composites should be obtained.

The schematic diagram of the specimen for fiber bundle pull-out test is shown in Fig.2(a). Figure 2(b) shows the magnification of warp/weft fiber crossing part. In order to cause the pull-out of warp fiber strand at the fiber crossing part, notches are introduced as shown in Fig.2. Moreover, to apply the shear force only to the fiber crossing part, a plate made by epoxy resin is placed on the both sides of fiber crossing part as shown in Fig.2(a). The geometry of the specimen was decided by finite element analysis in consideration of the stress components at fiber crossing part.

Fig.2 Schematic diagram of specimen for fiber bundle pull-out test.

Figure 3 shows the fracture process of fiber crossing part in fiber bundle pull-out test. Applying a load to the specimen, initial crack was occurred in the vertical direction to the load as shown in Fig.3. As the displacement increased, the delamination of fiber bundle progressed from the initial crack, and then the pull-out of warp fiber strand was observed. The fracture progress was independent of the concentration of silane coupling agents on a plain woven fabric. The strength of fiber crossing part was obtained by dividing the load at which initial crack occurred by the area of fiber crossing part.

Fig.3 Fracture process of fiber crossing part in fiber bundle pull-out test.

ANALYTICAL MODEL AND METHOD

In order to clarify the effects of fiber undulation and modulus of interface between fiber bundles on the shear deformation and strength at fiber crossing part, numerical analysis was performed by finite element method. Cross part model which represent the fiber crossing part was employed to consider the contact between undulated fiber bundles and the interface properties.

Figure 4 shows the finite element division for a fiber bundle pull-out test specimen and the boundary condition. The load was applied to one side of warp fiber strand as shown in Fig.4. In this study, three types of FE model with different crimp ratio were chosen. Crimp ratio is a unique characteristic in textile fabric which represent the degree of the fiber undulation and clearly the crimp ratio affects the mechanical behavior of textile composites. The FE model was composed of warp fiber strand, weft fiber strand, resin and interface elements. Two dimensional plain strain element was used in all elements. The material constants used in the model are shown in Table 1. The material constants of the fiber elements were calculated by Rule of Mixture since the fiber bundle was impregnated with the resin. The resin elements possess the properties of an epoxy resin. However, the material constants of the interface elements are unknown, because this relates to the interfacial properties between the fiber and matrix. Therefore, the elastic modulus of interface were changed on the basis of resin property, 1/10, 1 and 5 times as shown in Table 1. After all, nine kinds of analytical model with different crimp ratios and moduli of interface were examined as shown in Table 2. Hereinafter, abbreviated names in Table 2 is employed to express each model.

Fig.4 Finite element division for fiber bundle pull-out test specimen.

Table 1 Material constants used in FE model.

	Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Poisson's Ratio
Warp Fiber Strand	58.8	0.30
Weft Fiber Strand	17.0	0.03
Resin	3.4	0.33
Interface	0.34 / 3.4 / 17.0	0.33

Table 2 Analytical model with different crimp ratios and moduli of interface.

		Elastic modulus of interface (GPa)		
		0.34	3.4	17.0
Crimp ratio	0.22	BL	BM	BH
	0.15	ML	MM	MH
	0.10	SL	SM	SH

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 5 shows the deformation states of the MM model and ML model. In the case of the model with lower elastic modulus of interface than resin, the transmission of the strain of warp fiber strand through interface was smaller and the deformation of resin became smaller than that in the case of the model with higher elastic modulus of interface. The tendency was independent of the crimp ratio of the model.

Fig.5 Deformation states of ML model and MM model.

Second, initial fracture stress of the each model was investigated. Upon investigation of stress distribution on each element, clearly the initial fracture occurred at interface element. Figure 6 shows the initial fracture position at interface elements. The initial fracture position was changed with the crimp ratio and the modulus of interface elements. Figure 7 shows the relation between the normalized maximum stress at the interface and modulus of interface on each model with different crimp ratios. In this figure, the calculated maximum (von Mises) stress at the interface was normalized by dividing the applied stress to the warp fiber strand at each model. The normalized stress was also changed with the crimp ratio and the modulus of

interface elements. The maximum stress at the interface increased with increase either crimp ratio or modulus of interface.

Fig.6 Initial fracture position at interface elements.

Fig.7 Relation between normalized maximum stress at the interface and modulus of interface.

Finally, a new attempt was performed that the strength of interface was calculated by combining the numerical and experimental approaches. From the above numerical approach, the relation between the applied stress to the warp fiber strand and the calculated stress at the interface could be clarified. On the one hand, the shear strength of fiber crossing part could be obtained by experimental approach. In conjunction with the shear stress at which initial fracture occurred in experiments and the applied stress to the warp fiber strand in analysis, the stress calculated at the interface when the initial fracture occurred was obtained. This stress, indeed, is the strength of the interface.

The shear strength of fiber crossing part obtained by experiments with different concentration of silane coupling agents was ranging from 11.5 to 21.1 MPa. By using the strength, the strength of the interface was calculated with each model. Figure 8 shows the relation between modulus of interface and calculated strength of interface. In this case, since the crimp ratio and modulus of interface were unknown quantities, the strength could not be specified but the range of reasonable modulus and strength of interface could be clarified. Within the range, a proper combination of the modulus and strength should be fixed according to each interfacial treatment on fiber strand.

Fig.8 Relation between modulus of interface and calculated strength of interface.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, in order to study the deformation and fracture behavior at fiber crossing part in textile composites, an evaluation method of the interface between fiber bundles was examined by numerical approaches. The concept of modeling and numerical analysis model for textile composite was proposed and applied to fiber bundle pull-out test. The effects of crimp ratio and modulus of interface between fiber bundles on shear deformation and the stress at fiber crossing part was clarified. Finally, the strength of interface was calculated in conjunction with the shear stress at which initial fracture occurred in experiments and the applied stress to the warp finer strand in analysis. The introduced analytical model should be useful for investigation of the behavior at fiber crossing part in textile composites and further the determination the material constants of interface.

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